

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 1.4

***Report on WMO GTS datasets made available for non-GTS connected users
and on new datasets ingested into WMO GTS based on user requirements***

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Project

Arctic PASSION

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Lead beneficiary

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1. Introduction

The Arctic PASSION project is described in more detail in the project website which is available at <https://arcticpassion.eu/>. The purpose of Arctic PASSION is creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system. This implies integrating already existing observing systems in a system of systems approach as well addressing gaps in the current observing system. Arctic PASSION will generate data through the project implementation, but equally important is to map and establish access to already existing datasets in support of the pilot services and other activities of Arctic PASSION.

Arctic PASSION promised in the proposal to make existing data, that are currently difficult to access, more readily available. This was specifically referring to data available in the real time exchange of data within the world meteorological Organisation (WMO) and is limited to the data that are published as free and open data. A more thorough description of the real time exchange of data and which data that are available is given in [Section 2](#).

2. WMO GTS

The Global Telecommunication System (GTS) is "The co-ordinated global system of telecommunication facilities and arrangements for the rapid collection, exchange and distribution of observations and processed information within the framework of the World Weather Watch."

— <https://community.wmo.int/en/activity-areas/global-telecommunication-system-gts>

WMO Global telecommunication System (GTS) is a private network and is a key component of [WMO Information System](#) [<https://community.wmo.int/en/activity-areas/wis>]. With [WIS2.0](#) [<https://community.wmo.int/en/activity-areas/wis/WIS2-overview>], GTS is being replaced by a more modern approach based on a publish-subscribe approach relying on [MQTT](#) [<https://mqtt.org/>] which is a lightweight, publish-subscribe, machine to machine network protocol for message queue/message queuing service. When the transition from GTS to MQTT is finished, the WMO real time exchange of data will no longer happen in a private network but will use INTERNET as the transport mechanism. It is however, still a private network in the sense that it is made to serve the needs of WMO operational services. Details on how the system is set up is provided in the links above.

Regardless of whether GTS or WIS2 (MQTT) is used, the information conveyed in the system will be formatted in WMO formats BUFR^[1] and GRIB^[2]. These formats are pretty difficult to interpret and require specialised software and correct lookup tables.

Arctic PASSION is setting up a system to extract free and open information from the closed exchange of information through WMO channels and publish this as NetCDF files according to the [Climate and Forecast Conventions](#) [<https://cfconventions.org/>] with global attributes adhering to the Attribute Convention for Dataset Discovery (ACDD). In the process, the instantaneous measurements reported as messages in WMO channels are collocated into time series as well.

3. Approach towards improved access

Since MET is connected to GTS, observations from synoptic weather stations, radiosonde stations and ocean buoys are streamed to disk continuously. As indicated above, this information is available in BUFR (some gridded products like satellite and numerical simulations in GRIB). A software based on [ecCodes](https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/ECC) [https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/ECC] has been developed to replace previous data dumps which are now running on outdated software. The previous data dumps neither complied with discrete sampling geometries of CF-Conventions. Now data are dumped according to featureTypes: timeSeries, timeSeriesProfile and trajectoryProfile. A sample plot using the standard visualisation software [Panoply](https://www.giss.nasa.gov/tools/panoply/) [https://www.giss.nasa.gov/tools/panoply/] is shown in [Figure 1](#). The station shown is further described in [WMO Integrated Global Observing System](https://oscar.wmo.int/surface/#/search/station/stationReportDetails/0-20000-0-02038) [https://oscar.wmo.int/surface/#/search/station/stationReportDetails/0-20000-0-02038] (WIGOS). Since the data are dumped in a fully self describing file format, any standard software should be able to access and visualise the data. The information provided in [Figure 1](#) is all taken directly and automatically from the data file.

Figure 1. Air temperature from the Swedish station LATNIVAARA.

These data will be available through a [THREDDS Data Server](https://thredds.met.no) [https://thredds.met.no] operated by MET, properly described with discovery metadata and indexed in the [MET Arctic Data Centre](https://adc.met.no) [https://adc.met.no] which is feeding into the [SAON Data Portal](https://data.arcticobserving.org) [https://data.arcticobserving.org]. Data will be dumped to CF-NetCDF every 6 hour.

The primary focus of the approach in prioritised order has been to extract information from synoptic weather stations, radiosonde stations and ocean buoys. While testing it seems that more than 45 weather stations are available, and about 20 radiosonde stations. The number of ships and buoys reporting is highly variable. However, it is worth noting that these datasets are not generated by Arctic PASSION, the project is merely improving and simplifying access to these data for a larger number of users by exposing them outside the limited group that have access to them today. Furthermore, by ingesting them

into the SAON data portal, they are made easier discoverable.

4. Ingestion of new datasets

A requirement for ingestion of data into WMO GTS (and its replacement WIS 2.0) is that data are available in real or near real time. Furthermore, with the existing GTS operation through private networks (as opposed to Internet), there is a need for user community demand for the products, for e.g. feeding into numerical models, as bandwidth is limited. This latter requirement will be less prominent when the transition to WIS 2.0 and MQTT is fully done, but this is not expected until early 2030 at the earliest. So far there has been no real or near real time data streams announced by Arctic PASSION partners that would be suitable for ingestion. Nor has any Arctic PASSION partners identified third party datasets they think could be suitable for ingestion and subsequent use by e.g. the WMO modelling community. Thus no real time data has been made available for WMO GTS or MQTT (interface not available) yet.

However, work is in progress to make discovery metadata from the SAON Data Portal available for WIS 2.0 in order to announce the potential existence of new data when those finally becomes available. This is not ingestion and exchange of data (as discussed above), but adapting the discovery metadata announcing the existence of a dataset to the discovery mechanism of WIS 2.0. The reason for this is that WIS 2.0 relies on a totally different discovery protocol than what is normally used within scientific data management. This interface will contain both data generated by Arctic PASSION partners and third party datasets.

NOTE

Ingestion of data is a direct support for the Arctic PASSION community, with an opening for relevant third party datasets to be ingested (upon request from Arctic PASSION partners) if the appropriate contact and mutual understanding of sustainability can be established with the data provider.

5. Status

The software is nearing finalisation and is available in a [GitHub repository](https://github.com/steingod/bufr2netcdf) [https://github.com/steingod/bufr2netcdf] which is undergoing cleaning. Currently some modification of discovery metadata and final testing in the production environment is ongoing. This has revealed that updates to third party software (ecCodes) in the production environment is required before full deployment. Such upgrades are not done during freeze periods and the next opportunity for this upgrade is September 2024.

[1] Binary Universal Form for the Representation of meteorological data.

[2] General Regularly distributed Information in Binary form